

Title: When Adaptation Backfires: Lessons from Forest Firefighting on the Challenge of Balancing Dynamism and Stability in Multi-Team Systems.

Abstract: When studying coordination in challenging settings, the scientific literature shows two trends of results. On one hand, practice-oriented studies observe that many specialized groups of professionals rely on intense, adaptation-driven sequences of change to provide prompt and effective responses to high-stakes events. Ongoing adaptation is therefore viewed as a desirable outcome, leading researchers to promote dynamic, fast-paced, change-oriented sets of practices to overcome challenging situations. On the other hand, experiment-oriented studies suggest that these same groups of professionals may underperform or even break down due to the instability that comes with a high frequency of internal change. This leads to a contradiction: while adaptation is generally seen as a constructive phenomenon, its frequent occurrence may also have disruptive effects that could undermine the stability of an organized system. Such contradiction have not yet been fully explored and require further examination. It highlights a gap in understanding what are the potential tradeoffs of adaptation, particularly when performing fast response sequences of activity. We also need to better understand how individuals and groups deal with those specific tradeoffs. To this end, we argue that successful adaptation-driven systems must not only have the capacity to change rapidly but also mitigate disruptions induced by their own dynamism. In other words, internal or external factors must regulate the side effects of their change-oriented strategies to prevent system failure. We address this issue through the study of a forest firefighting operation (FFO) in the south of France during an intense fire season. Our findings show how adaptation can have detrimental effects on a system by increasing its overall instability. We also found that three internal factors help regulate the disruptive forces provoked by adaptation: the stabilizing actions of "architect" agents, the protective autonomy of sub-systems, and the existence of stable points of

convergence within the system itself. Our findings not only contribute to a more nuanced understanding of how adaptation impacts system stability but also provide insights for addressing the balance between rapid change and stability in fast-response settings.

Keywords : Adaptation, Multi-team Systems, Coordination, Crisis Management, Forest Firefighting.

Introduction:

Adaptation is a long-standing trend in the management research literature. While researchers do not always agree on the associated terminology, they typically use the concept to address “*intentional decision-making undertaken by organizational members, leading to observable actions that aim to reduce the distance between an organization and its economic and institutional environments*” (Sarta et al., 2021, p. 4). By doing so, they mean to describe a specific type of change, initiated by agents within an organized system and intended to increase convergence between that same system and its environmental characteristics. This concept becomes critical in the field of crisis management, where responsiveness to environmental change is seen as a key requirement to perform, especially when coordination is impeded by both ambiguity and discontinuity (Wolbers et al., 2018; Wolbers & Boersma, 2018). This is especially evident in studies that examine “fast response” sequences of activity, such as wildland fire control (Barton et al., 2015), post-disaster intervention (Kalkman, 2023), medical urgency (Faraj & Xiao, 2006), active shooter response (Schakel et al., 2016), counter-terrorism response (Wolbers, 2022), and high-speed pursuits (Schakel & Wolbers, 2021), where agents collectively aim to make a significant early impact on high-stakes events.

In these settings, researchers observe that many specialized groups of professionals enact various sets of adaptation-driven coordination practices, including role switching (Bigley & Roberts, 2001), plug-and-play teaming (Faraj & Xiao, 2006), organizational bricolage (Bechky & Okhuysen, 2011) or temporal semistructures (Uitdewilligen & Waller, 2011) while alternating between several modes of organizing to match the dynamism of the environment (Wolbers et al., 2018 ; Schakel & Wolbers, 2021). This ongoing and multilevel adaptation is seen as a key feature for successful operations and

fast-response coordination is described predominantly through highly dynamic sequences of internal change (Faraj & Xiao, 2006), while failure to perform in these settings is seen as the result of an inability to enact the right level of fluidity (Schakel & Wolbers, 2021). At the same time, other studies involving the Multi-Team System (MTS) model show that a high frequency of change is sometimes associated with disruptive forces that can ultimately lead to significant drops in performance in an organized system (Luciano et al., 2015; Fodor & Fleştea, 2016).

These contradictory results highlight a gap in the research literature. It also poses an unexpected dilemma for practitioners, as many fast-paced, change-oriented strategies observed in the field could be associated with specific trade-offs that have not been thoroughly investigated. From this perspective, adaptation could be seen as both a constructive and a disruptive phenomenon that may negatively impact performance at the system level. This would imply that organizations wishing to succeed in a fast-response sequence must not only increase their ability to change, but also find ways to regulate the self-induced instability that occurs during highly dynamic sequences. In other terms, we have yet to determine how an organized system can regulate the side effects of ongoing adaptation in order to prevent system failure during fast-response sequences of activity. This line of questioning is even more important in contexts where adaptation is taken for granted as a self-regulating phenomenon.

We will approach this question by investigating how an organized system behaves when engaging in fast-response coordination, which we define as “*a coordination sequence characterized by a high frequency of internal change and associated with a strong structural dynamism at the system level*”. Because they frequently engage with it, organizational arrangements described in research as “fast response organizations” (Faraj & Xiao, 2006) are useful for understanding both the challenges

that arouse in these sequences of activity and the practices that emerge to address them. Using the Multi-Team System model, we will explore a case study shaped by a narrative analysis of the Gignac-Saint-Bauzile operation, a forest firefighting operation (FFO) conducted in the Hérault department (France) in July 2022. Impacted by early setbacks and disrupted sequences of activity, this operation succeeded in controlling a major wildfire while preventing damage and casualties to several endangered hamlets. This case will help up to understand how a system can maintain or regain its performance while in a highly dynamic state.

Building on the idea that a high frequency of change may lead to instability and system failure, we will investigate how regulating and stabilizing mechanisms can help adaptation-driven systems maintain balance when engaging with the challenges of fast-response coordination. To this end, we wish to present three main findings from our case study. Firstly, we will explain how, despite benefiting from very good starting conditions, the operation suffered several declines in performance, prompting firefighters to engage in a fast-paced, adaptation-driven set of actions. Next, we will analyze how this strategy contributed to the instability of the system by pushing it into an “adaptation rush,” which led to new complications that further weakened its overall performance. Finally, we will argue that three regulatory factors played a crucial role in ultimately stabilizing the system, allowing it to regain its capacity for effective action: the work of “system architects,” the protective autonomy of sub-systems, and the existence of stable points of convergence within the system itself.

Part I : Theoretical framework: Fast paced coordination and the problem of disruptive adaptation:

As the field of crisis management continues to evolve, an increasing number of studies explore how agents coordinate efforts when they aim to make a significant early impact on high-stakes events (Barton et al., 2015 ; Kalkman, 2023 ; Faraj & Xiao, 2006 ; Schakel et al., 2016 ; Schakel & Wolbers, 2021 ; Wolbers, 2022). When studying these activities, researchers describe coordination predominantly through highly dynamic sequences of internal change, each of them seen as a “response” to everchanging environmental demands. This 'fast response' pattern of coordination—which gave rise to the concept of 'fast response organizations' (Faraj & Xiao, 2006)—is understood as “*a temporally unfolding and contextualized process of input regulation and interaction articulation to realize a collective performance*” (p.1157), emphasizing dynamism and responsiveness to environmental changes. It has been documented through the analysis of various sets of adaptation-driven coordination practices, such as role switching (Bigley & Roberts, 2001), plug-and-play teaming (Faraj & Xiao, 2006), organizational bricolage (Bechky & Okhuysen, 2011), temporal semistructures (Uitdewilligen & Waller, 2011) and switching between different modes of organizing at the system level (Wolbers et al., 2018 ; Schakel & Wolbers, 2021).

Adaptation -driven practice	Definition
Role switching	“[...] reassignment of personnel to different positions within the organization.” (Bigley & Roberts, 2001 ; p.1287)
Plug-and-play teaming (Faraj & Xiao, 2006)	Role-based ad hoc teaming, where experts can act interchangeably and the group can split up into functioning subunits (Faraj & Xiao, 2006)
Organizational bricolage	Combinaison of role-shifting, reorganizing routines and reordering the work (Bechky & Okhuysen, 2011).
Temporal semi structures	“[...] rhythmic shift in team focus” (Uitdewilligen & Waller, 2011 ; p.367)

Mode switching	Back and forth transitions between designed, frontline and partitioned organizing through command, allocation and information sharing processes (Schakel & Wolbers, 2021).
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Table 1 : Sets of adaptation-driven coordination practices observed in fast-response coordination sequences and their definition.

The emergence of these practices is generally attributed to a conscious effort to adapt rapidly to situations where coordination is impeded by both ambiguity and discontinuity (Wolbers et al., 2018). They lead to a “fragmented” coordination pattern (op. cit.), characterised by ad-hoc adaptations, separated pockets of control, and a multiplicity of interpretations. Unlike more stable patterns of coordination, fragmentation requires a high level of dynamism, which can be understood as *“the rate and intensity of structural changes in the system”* (Luciano et al., 2015; op. cit., p. 23). As a result, priorities, work processes, linkage between units, or even engagement with tasks, are rapidly changing as agents try to maintain adequacy with what they perceive as environmental demands (see Table 2). While this fragmentation pattern is considered by practice-oriented research as highly beneficial – if not necessary – for performing fast response coordination sequences (Wolbers et al., 2018; Schakel & Wolbers, 2021), the level of structural dynamism that it requires has been pointed out by other more experiment-oriented studies as being highly detrimental to performance, leading to serious downsides such as internal conflicts, uncontrolled shifts, or coordination breakdowns (Luciano et al., 2015; Shuffler et al., 2015).

Sub-dimensions of dynamism	Nature of changes	Observed downsides	Associated sets of practices
Changes in goal hierarchy	Shifts in priorities and goals.	Teams misalignment (DeChurch & Marks, 2006) ; Misattribution of resources (Luciano et al., 2015)	Fragmentation
Uncertainty of task requirements	Variations in work processes and procedures.	Perturbation of workflow (Luciano et al., 2015)	Organizational bricolage
Fluidity of system	Evolution in the	Disrupted communications (Crowe et	Role switching,

structural configuration	levels of interdependence between teams, power structures, communication networks, ...	al., 2014), Linkage instability (Vessey, 2014), Divided command (DeChurch et al., 2011 ; Marks et al., 2005).	Mode switching
Fluidity of system composition	Fluctuation in membership, team entering and leaving the system.	Impeded information sharing (Stoate, 2015 ; Fodor & Flestea, 2014 ; Flestea et al, 2017).	Plug-and-play teaming
Diversion of attention	Intermittency of teams' commitment to their task.	Uncontrolled interruption of tasks (Luciano et al., 2015)	Temporal semi structures

Table 2 : The five sub-dimensions of dynamism (Luciano et al., 2015) with associated change and observed downsides.

These results lead to a contradiction. On one hand, adaptation-driven practices are recognized as necessary to perform in fast-response sequences of activity. On the other hand, by generating a high frequency of change and impacting key structural features, these same practices are associated with serious declines in performance at the system level. This contradiction has not been thoroughly investigated by the literature, where adaptation is mostly seen as a self-regulating phenomenon. As a result, we lack a proper understanding of how or why dynamic systems are able to achieve and maintain a high level of performance, despite being disrupted by a high frequency of change. These challenges cannot be answered unless we consider that adaptation is both a constructive and disruptive phenomenon that have to be regulated *in situ* to create beneficial effects at the system level, which would imply that the system is somehow able to mitigate, buffer, compensate for, or even counteract disruptions induced by a high frequency of change.

For the purpose of this study, fast-response coordination will be understood as “*a coordination sequence characterized by a high frequency of internal change and associated with a strong structural dynamism at the system level*”. In their own way, each of our findings will expand the

litterature towards a better understanding of both coordination and adaptation. Firstly we will show that preemptive regulatory mechanisms (such as planning or information technologies) do not always have the capacity to regulate dynamism, especially when agents and teams engage in a fast-paced adaptation-driven set of actions. Secondly we will confirm that adaptation-driven strategies can have detrimental effects on a system by increasing its overall instability ; to this end, we will introduce the notion of “adaptation rush” to help us describe particular sequences characterized by a high frequency of adaptation-driven change. Finally, we will emphasize the importance of internal regulatory factors in stabilizing the system and ultimately allowing it to maintain or regain its expected level of performance despite the instability induced by its dynamism.

II. Making the case: an event-based approach:

1. Empirical setting :

In France, the term “rescue operation” (in French “opération de secours”) is a legal category that refers to “*a set of actions or decisions characterized by a strong degree of urgency and aiming to remove people, animals, goods and the environment from the damaging effects of accidents, catastrophes or threats.*” (Article L742-1 of the “Code de la Sécurité intérieure”). When applied to forest fire management, the same term refers to a specific organizational arrangement of specialized firefighting units, strongly integrated through a hierarchical structure and placed under the leadership of a unique commanding officer. Such operations rely on the coordinated actions of specific engines (ground or airborne), each one operated by a designated crew and integrated to a set of larger units through normalized role structures, procedures and communication network.

The intended general design of a forest firefighting operations (FFO) is detailed in the French national doctrine, although it may tolerate local variations. It presents certain resemblance with the Incident Command System (Bigley & Roberts, 2001), but presents several specificities that justify an overall presentation. In this research, we represent FFOs as a set of activities characterized by three major properties, based on the intended design set out in the national doctrine and taught in training schools. We will also take into consideration local characteristics relevant to our case study:

- 1- They follow a fast response pattern that can be described as a “one-fire-one-operation” principle;
- 2- They are adaptation-driven and rely heavily on centralization and fast-paced integration;
- 3- They are distinct from fire services, function as open systems and depend on external support provided by other organizations to get access to resources.

Firstly, a FFO is intended as a fast response activity, where all actions converge towards limiting fire propagation and preventing fire related damages and casualties. It is dedicated to a single fire, is created for the specific purpose of handling that fire and is dissolved once the fire is out. This “event-based logic”, which can be summarized as a “one-fire-one-operation” principle, leads to create a specific frame of reference for teams, by normalizing visualization tools and communication standards. The fire propagation axis becomes the reference point for all strategic planning and communication and any element of the operation site is described through its relation to the fire: flanks, front, rear, etc. This “one-fire-one-operation” principle is also associated with a “one-operation-one-commander” principle. As the fire increases in size, an operation can be divided into multiple subdivisions (generally geographical and/or functional sectors) but is intended to stay subordinate to one centralized command structure.

Secondly, because of the proximity between natural areas, human habitations and center of businesses in France, firefighting operations generally aim to obstruct the fire spread as quickly as possible to avoid adverse consequences. In order to achieve such goals, units are intended to rapidly converge and have a strong early effect on fire expansion. As a result, FFOs are usually very fluid systems, marked by a rapid adaptation rhythm and repeated reconfigurations throughout their life cycle. This intense dynamism is enacted through hierarchical integration as officers, whose training and professional culture is built around strategic planning and the coordination of decisive maneuvers, actively shape and reshape the system to fit their needs. The overall structure is supported by an advanced role structure, where each link in the chain of command (engine leaders, group leaders, etc.) belongs both to the team they lead and to a larger command team. This principle

of dual-positioning – based on dual-membership – leads to a specific kind of integration that we will call “embedded hierarchical integration”.

Figure 1: Example of a typical “embedded hierarchical integration” where engine leaders belong to both their own engine team and a command team at group level.

Finally, FFOs are better understood as open systems benefiting from external resources and support, rather than as part of a larger organization. Fire services and state agencies, which provides most of the staff, equipment and command structure, act as an embedding environment (Matthieu et al., 2001, p. 296) rather than as part of the system. This distinction more specifically allows for the addressing of the role of intermediary teams such as operation centers which connect the FFO with these organizations by interfacing with complex information management, strong logistic systems and extended coordination structures.

2. Data collection:

Due to the increasing presence of technology in the planning and conduct of operations, modern firefighting can now produce a lot of interesting firsthand raw data for research, such as live recordings (audio or video), satellite images, etc. When available, these data allow researchers to triangulate different sources of information and create an accurate representation of both fire spread and operational response. In most cases however, raw data are especially scarce. Particularly when firefighters are dealing with difficult situations, often characterized by coordination breakdowns, communication disruptions or interruptions, and an overall difficulty to control actions on the field. In these cases, most of the information about what happened is only available through narratives that will be created after the matter.

The term “narrative” is here used in a broad sense. Many documents, such as public or restricted reports, administrative inquiries or investigations, fall into that category as they all attempt, each in their own way, to retrospectively organize the facts and their perceptions in a cohesive and coherent way. This is especially true for events with important political and/or legal outcomes, where controlling the narrative becomes an important issue for groups and leaders. Confronting this difficulty inspired us to draw from the “narrative approach” (Giroux & Marroquin, 2005), by acknowledging that individuals – and later on, groups – engage in a narrative activity whenever calling back on certain events. Whatever their social utility might be (seeking recognition, assigning blame, ensuring conformity or creating an identity), these narratives all have the effect of aggregating, selecting, or dismissing facts, in a way that must be taken into account when these data are used for research.

This case study relies mainly on the testimonies of officers that have been involved in the conduct of the Gignac-Saint-Bauzile operation. We designed the interviews by adapting the “life story” method (Bertaux, 2010; Bah et al., 2015) and created an “event-based narrative approach” that would combine multiple narratives to produce a reliable account of the event. During each interview, after a brief phase of presentation, the interviewee was given a single prompt to produce a first-person account of their own experience of the event. The researcher then followed a “guidance process” (Breton, 2022) in order to regulate the pace and depth of the story.

Between December 2023 and November 2024, we conducted 15 interviews following this method. The selection of interviewee was based on an iterative process, each narrative leading to identify and select new potential respondents. The content of these narratives covered the entirety of the operation, with a strong prevalence of facts taking place in the first four hours, when the operation was the most critical. This core data was completed by different types of data provided by the departmental fire service of Hérault, such as audio recordings (from radio and specific phone communications), field reports, public reports, etc. They were treated as supplements and mostly used for triangulation. In that respect, they were never used as basis for designing guidelines or questions.

3. Data analysis:

The MTS model is intended to help researchers describe and analyze “*how interdependent teams operate as a larger work unit*” (op. cit, p. 292). Unlike most organizational models, its overall modeling approach is based on the assessment of the actual level of interdependence between teams. In order to be considered as part of the system, “[...] *each component must have input,*

process, and output interdependence with at least one other component team." (Mathieu et al., 2001, p. 295), which implies sharing resources (inputs), workflow (process) and outcomes (output). Therefore, any MTS based modelling will end up representing a tightly coupled network of teams (Marks et al., 2005, p. 965) that can be analyzed as a coherent whole.

The aim of our "event-based narrative approach" was to produce a reliable account of a specific event, using a baseline corpus of multiple narratives. In order to convert interviews into usable data, the main challenge was to establish both a temporal and logical order between facts. In other terms, we had to organize facts into a plausible sequence in order to allow cross referencing. To achieve this objective, our approach relied on a systematic, step by step, iterative process, where each interview was converted into an individual timeline before being integrated into a collective one. We designed this research method specifically to work on field operations, where most of the facts were not associated with a reliable timestamp or a precise spatial location.

The first step of the process was to convert each interview into an individual timeline. Facts were organized through the inner logic of the story, on both temporal (before/after) and logical (cause/effect) levels, without attempting to establish links with any other content. That logic was essential because all interviewees did not necessarily follow the same weave of storytelling and had created their own narrative more or less independently from one another. Once a narrative had been converted into an individual timeline, it was compared to the previous ones, looking for elements of convergence among them. During this first sequence, facts that were acknowledged by multiple narratives were identified as "anchors", that would help to articulate different timelines together.

In a second phase, facts that could be were triangulated in order to provide a strong structure to the data. Incomplete or missing information were filled in through logical reasoning. This was the case for tasks or activities whose duration could be estimated, such as transit time between one location to another. These different operations of cross-checking and supplementing contributed to create an “integrative timeline” that became more and more reliable overtime. Facts that were in contradiction with one another were sorted out by their overall credibility. This triangulation helped mitigating the risk of human error or misremembering, but also to remove interpretation biases from the researcher.

Source	hh:mm	Content	Observations
Reports and Interview.	11:30	<i>E6 gives a status report to the operation center. He reports 13 hectares burnt and ask for reinforcements. He informs the operation center that he has organized the operation in different sectors and that he intends to continue his reconnaissance mission. He estimates that trucks won't be able to follow the fire and need to go up front. He thinks that his rear left is covered by previous air drops. However, roads on the right flank have not be scouted.</i>	The time of the action is given in the command post written report at 12:41:53, as well as content of the status report. The author of the message is not identified (called "COS Pellican"). We attributed it to E6 by deduction.

Table 3 : Extract from integrative timeline.

At the end of the process, we presented a written version of the overall narrative to all participants during a focus group session in November 2024. This final phase allowed us to clear out any ambiguity or misinterpretation of facts that would have occurred during the triangulation phase. It therefore contributed to increase the validity of both our integrative timeline and final narrative.

III. A narrated account of the operation:

1. Set up conditions :

The event took place in late July 2022 between the small municipalities of Gignac, Saint-Bauzile-de-la-Sylve, Aumelas and St-Paul-et-Valmale, located approximately 25 kilometers from the city of Montpellier (south of France). Situated between two major plains, the area was made of several rugged hills covered with woods and low vegetation. Despite proximity to both a densely populated area and the A75 highway, the local population density was quite low. Inhabitants were mainly concentrated into two hamlets, within the municipality of Aumelas, with some agricultural land scattered across the plateau. The area was also quite isolated, with only a few roads and pathways running through the landscape. However, due to its proximity to several protected landscapes, it was clearly identified by the firefighters as of great importance.

The summer of 2022 was particularly hot and dry in France. July was marked by an intense heat wave from the 12th to the 25th, following an earlier wave in May. This led to intense dryness of both land and vegetation. With the exception of a few thunderstorms at the beginning and end of the month, rainfall was scarce and very light, often less than 5 mm, or even non-existent. As a result, several French departments faced more frequent and more significant wildfires throughout the month. To help face this difficult situation, the departmental fire service of Hérault could rely on significant resources dedicated to forest firefighting. Officers and crews were trained and familiar with both forest firefighting techniques and strategies, airborne resources were quickly available for reconnaissance, ground support or tactical actions, and several locations were covered by early detection systems, such as video monitoring and patrols.

Additionally, since the beginning of the summer season, ground forces were regularly pre-positioned in the most sensitive areas. In order to maximize reactivity, these units were pre-organized into Forest Fire Intervention Groups (FFIG), each group consisting of four Forest Fire Tankers (FFT) and one reconnaissance vehicle driven by a group leader officer. The day of the event, the pre-positioning process of these dedicated ground forces was planned between 11am and 1pm. It was intended to achieve full capacity by 2pm, when the risk of fire outburst was highest. Concurrently, a dedicated ops room was set up in the operation center, in order to take on any forest fire related alerts. Finally, officers on call were gathering regularly around 9am to conduct a strategy meeting and to drill procedures and equipment.

2. Fire outbreaks and early response :

Figure 2: Location of the two fire outbreaks (1 and 2) and area burned by the fire (source : ONF).

On Tuesday the 26th of July 2022, at approximately 10:20am, the departmental fire service of Hérault (France) received a call reporting a forest fire starting near the A75 freeway and the little

town of Gignac. Using remote cameras, operators identified not one but two outbreaks of fire only one kilometer apart, already threatening vineyards and woodland. Judging from their locations and the environmental conditions, including a strong eastward wind pushing them towards the hills, the operation center officers rapidly understood that the fires would be critical. At the same time, firefighters from a nearby fire station spotted two columns of smoke. The two officers on call (Lieutenant Guy., group leader, and Commandant Dan., column leader) set off, each driving a reconnaissance vehicle. Also present at the fire station, members of the departmental air patrol made themselves ready to take off. Between 10:35 and 10:40am, the operation center mobilized an additional group leader (Capitaine Zyn.), several FFTs and the air patrol helicopter.

Ranks	Lieutenant	Capitaine	Commandant	Lieutenant-Colonel	Colonel
NATO code	OF1	OF2	OF3	OF4	OF5

Table 4 : French ranks and their respective NATO code.

In less than 5 minutes, the helicopter arrived on site and initiated a first reconnaissance. The officers on board called for air reinforcements – both at the local and national level – and started video recording to give the operation center a better view of the situation. As the ground force were still in transit, the Commandant Nil., who was commanding the air patrol, coordinated the first airdrops on the Gignac fire, which he thought was more dangerous. Meanwhile, Lieutenant Guy. and Commandant Dan. were still making their way on two separate routes, as they had agreed in advance to set up two separate operations. The first would deal with the fire furthest to the left (North-side, called “Gignac”), closer to the highway, while the second would handle the fire furthest to the right (South-side, called “Saint-Bauzile”). Anticipating that the fire would quickly spread beyond his competences, Lieutenant Guy. called out to the local commander, Lieutenant Sen., qualified as column leader, to assist him.

Figure 3: Map of system interdependencies at 10:45

At around 11:00am., Lieutenant Guy., Capitaine Zyn. and Commandant Dan. arrived on site and began to scout the area. At the same time, based on the information provided by the air patrol and their own remote cameras, the operation center officers decided to alert higher-level officers and to set up a command post, in order to rapidly organize a united larger scale operation. From their point of view, the initial two operations would soon merge and become the left and right sectors of a unique operation. A site leader officer, Lieutenant-Colonel Jon., and several others were called in. For their part, at 11.15 and 11:20am, Commandant Dan. and Lieutenant Sen. (who had taken over the Gignac operation, initiated by Lieutenant Guy.) respectively took command of their operations. Despite their geographical proximity, they conducted their operation separately and each asked for dedicated resources from the operation center. For both of them, the main objective was to rapidly build up a capacity to take actions, as resources available were still too low to affect fire progression.

At approximately the same time, substantial ground and air forces began to arrive on site – as well as several officers – and most of the remaining isolated FFTs were rapidly aggregated into FFIGs. Confused by the proximity of the two fires, most of the reinforcements joined the Gignac operation, where the command post had just arrived and where one air patrol officer, Commandant Sam., had taken the role of air-liaison officer (see IV-1). As a result, most of the ground and air forces concentrated on the left part of the field, leaving the Saint-Bauzile operation isolated both geographically and structurally. Still pushed by a strong eastward wind, left free on both the center and the right part of the field, the fires gained strength and began to threaten the Aumelas hamlets, located farther East.

Figure 4: Map of system interdependencies at 11:30am

Just before 12:00pm, Lieutenant-Colonel Jon. arrived on scene and took command of both operations. Despite having been urged by the operation center to rapidly fuse the two operations, he decided to maintain a distinction between them, arguing that the fires were still clearly separated

and that it was both impossible and dangerous to work in the area between them. He took command of both operations and instructed Lieutenant Sen. (Command Team “Gignac”) and Commandant Dan. (Command Team “St-Bauzile”) to keep their perimeters and avoid getting caught between the two fires at all costs. Focused on the tactical level and preoccupied by the endangered hamlets, Lieutenant-Colonel Jon. gave his status report to the operation center and prepared to leave on an aerial reconnaissance mission.

Soon after, a number of senior officers arrived on the scene and the Lieutenant-Colonel Jon. instructed them to join the command structure, leading to new changes. Lieutenant-Colonel Dan. took over the Gignac operation and Lieutenant-Colonel Lum. briefly took on the role of air-liaison officer for the Saint-Bauzile operation, but quickly resigned due to communication failures. Other officers, such as Colonel Ato., stayed back in order to let the operations stabilize and to help with coordination. At this stage of the operation, neither the commander, the command post nor the operation center had any direct control over the resources deployed in the field. The quality of radio exchanges was poor, both between the commander – who was engaged in air reconnaissance – and his command team, and among the officers themselves.

Furthermore, the proximity between the two fires made it difficult to give instructions from a distance, as landmarks and markers were often confused. Officers were forced to command by sight and voice, and to concentrate their resources around them. Pressed forward by the advancing fire, Capitaine Zyn. (Command Team “Group 1”), Lieutenant Guy. (Command Team “Group 2”) as well as Lieutenant Sen. and Commandant Dan. moved to the front, with all the land resources at their disposal, to defend the hamlets of Aumelas. Comprised of resources originated from both operations, this mixed force experienced real difficulty communicating and coordinating, as radio

signals were impaired by the nearby hills but also by recent changes in the command structure (see part IV-2). Only the airborne units, still coordinated by Commandant Sam. were left holding the leftmost flank, defending the freeway.

Figure 5: Map of system interdependencies at 12:40pm.

3. From a critical phase to a stabilization process :

Between 12:00am and 1:00pm, the operation entered a critical phase in terms of resources, structure and overall efficiency. Firstly, the flow of new land forces was at a low point, as the first wave, formed by vehicles and crews based in nearby fire stations, had come to an end. The operation center started to call in resources that were based further away and even outside the department. Simultaneously, a controversy arose over whether to maintain the separation of operations sought by the Lieutenant-Colonel Jon. or abandon it to merge the two operations. Doubts arose about the

number of resources available, and the command post experienced great difficulties in evaluating how many reinforcements had already come in. Finally, both fires were now converging on the hamlets of Aumelas, where they would arrive at greater force.

At around 1:30pm, at the command post, Colonel Ato. decided that the flanks of the two fires were now too close together, creating a dangerous overlap in terms of airborne safety. He also felt that the command post was too isolated and would not be able to keep up with the situation. He took over command of both operations and actively worked towards merging them.

Figure 6: System map at 2:00pm.

At 1:57pm, after carrying out a first series of directives (security measures, perimeters assignments, etc), Colonel Ato. informed the operation center that the Gignac and Saint-Bauzile operations had been effectively merged, and that the command post was to be transferred to a new location. At this

stage, a great deal of organizational work still needed to be done to enable the new operation to function. Shortly after 2:30pm, less than an hour after the merging of operations, the Gignac and Saint-Bauzile fires met up in front of the endangered hamlets and accelerated towards the houses. With Lieutenant Sen. (now Command Team “Aumelas 1”) and Commandant Dan. (now Command Team “Aumelas 2”) in place, the ground forces were in position to defend the properties. The fight was particularly difficult: the firefighters had to stay under the black smoke of the combined fires and a truck was caught in the flames, needing air support to extricate itself. Though the fire reached the hamlets of Aumelas, the defense was still successful in stopping its progression before it reached any property within the hamlet. Interrupted in its progress, the fire slid off to the left, taking a turn north, into a nearby valley.

On site, other firefighters were already waiting for the fire. In fact, the implementation of a unified operation had made it possible to anticipate the fire sliding and provided Lieutenant-Colonel Lum. with the means to block it at the crossroad between routes D114 and D139. Shortly after 3:00pm, as the fire reached their position, several Hérault Forest Fire Intervention Groups (GIFF) and columns of reinforcements from nearby departments were already in position, supported by airborne resources. This maneuver was intended to be decisive and to stop the fire spreading. However, the firefighters had very little time to prepare and were unable to deal with all the fire's sudden surges, due to the rugged landscape and several coordination failures. At around 4pm, the fire escaped and continued to spread to the left, threatening new areas.

Despite this, the results were mainly positive. No houses were touched by fire, and there were no serious injuries among the firefighters. Moreover, the operation now had a stable architecture, enabling it to integrate new resources and step up its anticipation work. The operation enters a new

phase. At 4:20pm, Colonel Ben., Deputy Director General of the fire service, took over as new commanding officer. The main challenge was now to protect the village of Saint-Paul-et-Valmale, farther East. Advanced tactics involving backfires and fire retardants were mobilized to stem the progress of the fire, and a defensive barrier was set up near the village. At the end of the day, nightfall considerably slowed the intensity of the fire. The next day, at 9.30am, the prefecture of Hérault announced that the head of the fire was no longer progressing. At a further update at 3:30pm, it was publicly announced that the fire was now under control.

IV. Case study results :

1. Early setbacks and initial imbalance within the system:

At first sight, both Gignac and Saint-Bauzile operations benefited from very good starting conditions. The two outbreaks of fire were spotted and localized very quickly, leading to early deployment orders and quick reactions from several key actors of the intervention. Airborne reconnaissance provided useful information for the operation center to rapidly grasp the importance of the situation and alert higher level of command. However, the overall Gignac-Saint-Bauzile system suffered from several drops in performance during its early stages of development: as a result, for more than 4 hours, despite an early intervention and considerable resources on site, it was impossible for the firefighters to have a significant impact on fire progression. Overall, 951.8 hectares were consumed by the fire, making it the department's most destructive since 2010. The operation involved around 650 firefighters, including 150 reinforcements from other departments, as well as specialized military units and airborne forces. Our study reveals that three set up conditions played a role in this early sequence of low performance : the abnormal launch time; the geographical proximity between the two outbreaks; and a series of dysfunctions in the radio based communication network.

Firstly, the launch time of both operations (around 10:30 am), impaired the system's development in two places: on one hand, ground forces were not yet pre-positioned; on the other, many of the duty officers were attending a ceremony organized in the commune of Clapiers, on the eastern side of Montpellier. As a result, many anticipated resources were not immediately available, and the early stages of the operation had to be provided with whatever was at hand, including self-engaged

staff. Preemptive regulatory mechanisms, such as extensive planning or anticipated measures for the day, could not take full effect. This situation forced firefighters to build up the system from partial arrangements, and to alternate between applying previously validated plans and improvising new ones. For example, a divergence emerged between the operation center and the commanding officers on whether to merge the two operations or not. Having benefited from early air patrol reports and having seen the fires on camera, the operation center's officers actively prepared to merge the two operations while the command teams were still trying to operate and build their actions in a separate mode. Far from being the result of any deliberate choice or tactical planning, this divergence is mostly the result of an early shift within the system, when several trends of adaptation started to emerge more or less independently.

Secondly, the initial geographical proximity between the two operations complicated the overall organization of the fight. Due to the “one-fire-one-operation” logic, ambiguity arose between the firefighters when describing the intervention zone, especially when communicating at a distance by radio or phone. For example, because the left flank of the Saint-Bauzile operation corresponded to the right flank of the Gignac operation, the two designations were used interchangeably in exchanges and reports. The passing of instructions, generally based on the assignment of a perimeter of action (left flank, right flank, front, etc.), was therefore greatly complicated, as well as the identification and tracking of staff on the field. It became difficult for agents to identify their place within the system, which depended on their position in relation to the fire. The proximity between them also disrupted the routing of reinforcements, increasing the risk of error when arriving on the scene.

Thirdly, due to geographical location (rugged hills, isolated from populated areas), radio-based communication network failed regularly during the earliest stages of the operations, leading most firefighters to use their cellphone to communicate between them. This particular arrangement led many exchanges to be had between two individuals rather than on collective open radio channels. If this solution still allowed information to be shared to some extent, it further contributed to fragment the system.

These three initial conditions quickly led to an imbalance which rapidly evolved into an indirect competition between the two operations for material and human resources. Because of its more “advantageous” geographical position, the Gignac operation quickly took precedence over the Saint-Bauzile operation. It absorbed the majority of early ground and airborne resources and massively deployed them on the far-left flank, opposite the Saint-Bauzile fire. More isolated, the Saint-Bauzile operation came late in acquiring its first ground resources, relying on reinforcements that arrived through secondary routes, or on groups directly taken from the Gignac operation. It also benefited from only a limited number of airdrops in the early stages, with airborne resources being concentrated primarily on the Gignac operation.

This underlying competition can be seen in how the system shaped over time despite considerable efforts to create two separated and equally provided operations. Figures 4 and 5 provide a clear picture on how teams converged towards the Gignac command team, shifting the center of mass of the entire system. Combined with previously addressed complications, this imbalance impaired the system development and contributed significantly to its initial under-performance. However, these early setbacks cannot totally explain why it was so difficult for the firefighters to have a significant initial impact on fire progression. More than being the ultimate cause for the system’s under-

performance, it appears that these organizational setbacks acted as a trigger for an early “adaptation rush” that further destabilized the system.

2. The disruptive effects of adaptation:

From the firefighters’ perspective, the initial fragility and low performance of the system called for early adaptations: based on their understanding of the situation, operatives, crew members and officers alike implemented a number of changes in order to regain a capacity to take decisive actions that would impact fire progression. Many behaviors fall into that category and can be linked to a sub-dimension of dynamism (Luciano et al., 2015) : higher officers taking charge, communication channels being rearranged and redistributed (fluidity of system configuration), oscillation between a two-fires-two-operations and a two-fires-one-operation logic (uncertainty in task requirements), teams entering the system or being dispatched (fluidity of system composition), new roles and priorities being attributed (change in goal hierarchy), etc. As the system increased in size, these attempts quickly multiplied and conducted to increase the frequency of change as well as the overall disruption level of the system. In that sense, the beginning of the Gignac-St-Bauzile operation may be considered as an “adaptation rush”, which can be understood as a particular sequence characterized by a high frequency of adaptation-driven change.

Consistently with the idea debated in the MTS framework that a high level of system dynamism imposes several drawbacks to a highly coupled system of teams, our case study results show that an adaptation rush may lead to more or less localized system failure, as many examples highlight the disruptive effects of a high frequency of adaptation-driven change. One of the most illustrative can be found in the early defense of the Aumelas’ hamlets, when Lieutenant Sen. and Commandant

Dan. temporarily lost the ability to coordinate due to changes in the command structure. At 12:31pm, after joining the command team of Colonel Jon., Lieutenant-Colonel Din. took over the Gignac operation and created a new command team (see Figure 5). This adaptation of the Gignac operation was carried out according to standard FFO tactical mindset and aimed to optimize resource management and planning. Separated radio channels were created, to prevent distant units from interfering with each other, inadvertently leading Lieutenant Sen. and Commandant Dan. (which had been placed on the same radio frequency for the first time at 12.15pm by Colonel Jon.) to be unable to communicate while both defending the same area.

Far from being deliberate, an adaptation rush can only be understood if we take into account that each actor acts according to his or her own representation of both environment state and system state. Each transformation of the system is therefore based on a localized attempt to propose an adapted response to immediate and/or anticipated challenges. This perspective highlights the fact that adaptation in a multi-team system is both poly-chronous and poly-centric, which means that it must be considered on multiple timelines and multiple places at once. In that sense, the threat caused by an unregulated adaptation rush may be even greater when adaptation becomes a circular process: as instability increases due to previous adaptations, more attempts are made to implement change at different locations within the system. Without any regulating process, an adaptation-driven system could very well fall into an “adaptation loop”, when the frequency of change never stops increasing, to the point where it leads to a system failure.

3. Regulatory factors and their stabilization effects:

The fact that adaptation may become a circular and overly disruptive process within a system forces us to ask a simple question. How can we explain that, despite an early sequence of under-performance and several system failures, the Gignac-Saint-Bauzile operation did not evolve into a generalized system breakdown? What mechanisms allowed the system to maintain its integrity during the most dynamic sequences or at least to stabilize rapidly after them? By investigating this particular question in our case study analysis, we identified three regulatory factors that helped to mitigate self-induced disruptions at the system level : the work of “system architects”, the protective autonomy of sub-systems and the existence of stable points of convergence within the system itself.

Firstly, by focusing on the internal structure of the system rather than on tactical actions to be taken, various agents developed a stabilizing influence throughout the operation. These individuals focused on creating and strengthening the system’s architecture, by integrating resources, fixing structural malfunctions or maintaining relations throughout the system. Officers that had the opportunity to take over the operation – in part or in totality – or to edict new tactical priorities renounced it to focus on integrating the first reinforcements, enabling the overall system to rapidly benefit from functional groups of vehicles. This was, for instance, the case with Colonel Ato., who only took over the operation an hour after his arrival, and spent the next hour reconfiguring the structure rather than initiating new tactical decisions. Because these “system architects” were focused on supporting action rather than acting themselves, they were able to compensate several phases of instability.

Secondly, in the absence of a centralized decision-making structure, actions in the field were essentially thought out and carried on by group and column leaders in contact, who took initiatives according to the issues they perceived, but also according to the means available to them directly. As a result, relatively independent sub-systems emerged and were able to maintain their internal coordination as well as defining their own objectives. These self-reliable groups were less sensitive to structural changes and were able to continue action despite the impossibility of coordinating with others. In other words, the fragmented nature of the system protected the integrity of several units and prevented instability from spreading. It is undoubtedly the autonomy of these sub-systems that enabled early convergence on the Aumelas hamlets, at a time when neither the successive operation leaders nor the command post had any real control over actions on the ground. It also helped compensate several coordination issues. For instance, when defending the hamlets, units created an effective line of defense without a centralized decision making or extensive communication network.

On a more general note, it can be observed that system dynamism – induced in this case by adaptation – was not uniformly distributed throughout the system. In that sense, by increasing their own stability and performance, certain parts of the system, whether specific agents, teams or technical sub-systems, also contributed to reducing the system's instability. In other terms, a partial systemic constancy somewhat balanced instability. For example, in the case of the Gignac-Saint-Bauzile operation, the coordination of airborne resources remained highly stable throughout the operation by keeping the same air-liaison officer (membership constancy) and the same means of communication with both airborne resources and the command post (linkage constancy). The early presence of the air patrol and the transferring of Commandant Sam. from the air patrol to the role of air-liaison officer, allowed the Gignac operation (and later, the Gignac-Saint-Bauzile operation) to

benefit from a structured air-ground liaison from the start and to endure several highly disrupted sequences of activity. To that extent, stable parts of the system acted as anchors for the other elements of the system, encouraging convergence in action.

Conclusions and Discussion

The Gignac-Saint-Bauzile case provides fruitful insights on how adaptation-driven systems behave when facing a high degree of instability. By applying the MTS model and a narrative approach to our case-study, we have been able to map several sequences of change, allowing us to see the tangible impact of adaptation on an organized system. Building on the idea that a high frequency of change may lead to instability and system failure, we have shown how an adaptation-driven strategy could strongly contribute to system instability by pushing it into an “adaptation rush”, which could weaken its overall performance instead of improving it. We also found that different internal factors can help to regulate the disruptive forces provoked by adaptation. Our case-study identified three of these: the stabilizing action of “architect” agents, the protective autonomy of sub-systems, and the existence of stable points of convergence within the system itself.

By fully taking into consideration the disruptive effects of adaptation, our research has shown that adaptation-driven system must benefit from stabilizing factors in order to survive their most dynamic states. When considering adaptation mostly as an “*intentional decision making undertaken by organizational members*” (Sarta et al., 2021 , p. 4), authors may overlook the particular tension that arise at the system level, where adaptation becomes both part of the problem and part of the solution. By saying that, we want to draw the attention on the importance of system inner-stability rather than on the quality of the decision-making. In fact, rather than drawing a line between “constructive” and “disruptive” adaptation, we wish to highlight the fact that any adaptation has in itself a disruptive potential that must be regulated by stabilizing mechanisms.

To that extent, our hypothesis is that drawbacks mostly occur when the frequency of changes exceeds the system's capacity to stabilize, despite the inner-quality of the decision. In that sense, our findings are supplementing the MTS based literature by identifying key features that allow dynamic systems to achieve and maintain a high level of performance despite their self-induced disruptions. The three regulatory factors we highlighted provide a first step in that direction, but other factors may be found in other settings. We should also address how each of these factors operates in itself, as they ask important questions that are not necessarily addressed by the literature. For firefighting operations, the most crucial of them might be the question of autonomy, and how it interacts with both centralized decision making and hierarchical integration.

These results have important implications for practitioners. By design, forest firefighting operations are intended as adaptation-driven systems. The command teams are encouraged to shape the system as quickly as possible to keep up with a volatile and adverse environment. The priority is therefore given to the tactical domain, and both the quality and fluidity of decision making is seen as the most important factor for performance. System architecture is thus considered as a byproduct of tactical decisions, meant to ensure the reliability of actions and avoid safety problems. By highlighting the link between adaptation and instability, the case of the Gignac-Saint-Bauzile operation illustrates the fact that any tactical decision must first find the right systemic conditions to be effective. In other terms, the tactical domain must be balanced by the architectural domain.

When facing critical contexts, marked by the destabilization of the whole structure, constructing and maintaining a stable system is a necessary condition if decisions are to be carried out. Otherwise, by further weakening the system, well thought out adaptation may ultimately lead to system failure.

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